

PERCEPTION OF THE AFFECTIVE FOCUS OF SCHOOL SUBJECTS

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ABSTRACT

Education is the process of facilitating learning, or the acquisition of knowledge, skills, values, beliefs, and habits. Proper and good education is very important for all. It facilitates quality learning all through the life. Quality learning includes holistic development of child through education that includes the drawing out of the best from the subjects and offering them to the students. The study aims to find out how students and teachers perceive the affective focus of the school subjects. While the students' opinion was sought regarding History and Science, the teachers' opinion was taken with reference to all the subjects. Also, the factors that hinder value inculcation through school subjects, were identified. The study thus provides insights regarding the affective domain that has so far not considered seriously.

Key words: *Affective, Perception, Values, School Subjects.*

INTRODUCTION

'Educating the mind without educating the heart is no education at all.' These words of Aristotle are of paramount importance to educators. While a lot of focus has been given by school education to develop the mind, very less attention is given to the affective domain. Blame this on increasing Consumerism and the world shrinking due to Globalization and Liberalization. The focus of education has tilted more towards meeting the needs of the competitive world. Hence the various school subjects are seen as gateways to revenue generation rather than value generation. Each subject in the secondary school curriculum has its own value and significance. Besides disseminating information for the mind, the subjects have intrinsic values embedded in them. They need to be unearthed by the teachers during the teaching learning process in order that students are able to perceive the same. Students already have formed certain impressions about the various subjects. What the students think about the subjects, speak a lot about the way the subject is transacted, Hence, it needs to be seen what the students think about the affective focus of the school subjects.

The Affective focus of a subject is operationalized for the study as the inclination of a subject to develop values among its learners. Very often it is perceived that different subjects have varying objectives. Humanities and languages are seen as subjects catering to the Affective domain, while Science and Mathematics are considered to be predominantly for the Cognitive Domain. It is these perceptions that could shape the interest of the students towards the subjects. Hence it needs to be seen what really is the general perception of learners regarding the Affective focus of the subjects.

Attitudes and values are caught rather than taught. Teachers play a major role in disseminating not only the information regarding the subjects, but also incidentally transmitting their perception towards a particular subject. Hence it is essential to see how teachers perceive the affective focus of different subjects. For the present study, History and Science have been considered for opinion from students. Teachers were studied with reference to the opinion regarding all the school subjects.

VARIABLES OF THE STUDY

Dependent Variable: Students' Perception regarding the Affective Focus of the School Subjects, History and Science

Independent Variable: Teachers' opinion regarding the Affective Focus of School Subjects in General

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The objectives of the study were as follows;

- a. To study the perception of secondary school students regarding the affective focus of the subjects;
 - History
 - Science
- b. To study the perception of secondary school teachers regarding the affective focus of the subjects.

HYPOTHESIS OF THE STUDY

1. There is no significant difference in the Affective focus of the subjects- History and Science as perceived by secondary school students.
2. There is no significant difference in the Affective focus of the subjects- History and Science as perceived by secondary school teachers.

SAMPLE

An available total sample of 51 number of students of Std. 8th from two schools were taken for the study. The number of teachers considered for the study were 32.

TOOLS USED FOR THE STUDY

- **Questionnaire for Students' Perception of the Affective Focus of School Subject – History** -The options for each question were: Agree, Disagree and Not decided
- **Questionnaire for Students' Perception of the Affective Focus of School Subjects – Science** -The options for each question were: Agree, Disagree and Not decided

METHOD OF STUDY

For the present study the researcher used the Descriptive Survey method.

DATA ANALYSIS

The analysis was done with reference to Students' Perception and Teachers' Perception.

I) Students' Perception

The statements of the tool were each analyzed to find out their Percent Mean Significance. The following graphs (Fig. 1 and 2) show the number of statements showing the Magnitude of the Percent Means

Figure 1 : Graph Showing the Magnitude of Statements with Reference to History

Figure 2 :Graph Showing the Magnitude of Statements with Reference to Science

The above graphs show that the subject History seems to be perceived as having more Affective Focus than Science. The Descriptive Statistics for History and Science are as follows;

TABLE 1 : DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS OF THE SCORES ON THE PERCEPTION REGARDING HISTORY AND SCIENCE

Subjects	Mean	Standard Deviation
History	$M_1 = 38.32$	$\sigma_1 = 4.89$
Science	$M_2 = 35.42$	$\sigma_2 = 5.75$

Figure 3 :Graph Showing the Mean Scores of The Two Subjects

It is found here that the students perceive History as having a greater Affective Focus than the subject Science.

Testing Hypothesis 1:

The hypothesis is stated as;There is no significant difference in the Affective focus of the subjects- History and Science as perceived by secondary school students.

TABLE 2: Inferential Statistics of the Perception of Secondary School Students Regarding the Subjects History & Science

Subjects	Mean	Standard Deviation	t-value	Level of Significance	Status of Significance
History	M ₁ = 38.32	σ ₁ = 4.89	3.08	0.01	Significant
Science	M ₂ = 35.42	σ ₂ = 5.75			

CONCLUSION: The ‘t’ value is found to be significant, hence the hypothesis that there is no significant difference in the Affective focus of History and Science is rejected.

INTERPRETATION: There is a **significant difference** between the two subjects in their Affective Focus. History is perceived by students as having a higher Affective focus than Science.

II Teachers’ Perception

The Descriptive Statistics of The Perception of Teachers Regarding the Affective Focus Of School Subjects in general was done for;

1. The Affective focus of various School Subjects
2. Factors influencing the Affective focus of School subjects

Table 3 :Mean Scores of The Affective Focus of Subjects as Perceived by Teachers

SUBJECTS	MEAN SCORES
Languages	4.81
Science	4.48

Mathematics	3.52
History	4.52
Geography	4.05

Figure 4 :Graph Showing The Affective Focus Of Subjects As Perceived By Teachers

Table 4

Mean Scores of The Factors Influencing the Affective Focus of Subjects as Perceived by Teachers

Factor No.	Statement Of The Factor	Mean Scores
1	Too much focus on academics	2.38
2	Education is marks oriented	2.19
3	Curriculum does not offer much scope	1.67
4	Syllabus content does not lend itself to value development	1.62
5	There is not much time to complete the syllabus	2.29
6	Large number of students in a class	3.19
7	Students are not interested in feelings, emotions and values	2.24
8	School cannot do much because of the strong media influence	2.19

From the above figures it can be said that-

1. The teachers are of the opinion that the subject that has the highest Affective focus is Languages.
2. The teachers are of the opinion that the subject that has the least Affective focus is Mathematics.
3. The teachers feel that the factor that influences value development most is Large number of students in a class followed by too much focus on academics and less time to complete the syllabus.

FINDINGS

For Hypothesis 1;

There is a **significant difference** between the two subjects in their Affective Focus. History is perceived by students as having a higher Affective focus than Science.

For hypothesis 2;

- i. The teachers are of the opinion that the subject that has the highest Affective focus is Languages.
- ii. The teachers are of the opinion that the subject that has the least Affective focus is Mathematics.
- iii. The teachers feel that the factor that influences value development most is; Large number of students in a class followed by too much focus on academics and less time to complete the syllabus.

CONCLUSION

Students perceive what they receive. History being a Social Studies subject, is perceived as naturally lending itself to development of values. However, the values inherent in Science is not made visible to the students. It is therefore important to show how humanity is indebted to Science. Concerted efforts would need to be made by schools and also teachers to ensure that subjects do not only remain in the cognitive domain, but also touch the heart and the hand.

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